

APÊNDICE B - LISTA DE ARTIGOS MAPEADOS NA LITERATURA

ID	Titulo	Autores
1	Employee Retention and Turnover in Global Software Development: Comparing in-House Offshoring and Offshore Outsourcing	Bass, Julian M. and Beecham, Sarah and Razzak, Mohammed Abdur and Noll, John
2	Motivation and Autonomy in Global Software Development: An Empirical Study	Noll, John and Razzak, Mohammad Abdur and Beecham, Sarah
3	A Project Management Framework for Global Software Development	Jain, Ritu and Suman, Ugrasen
4	Antecedents of Turnover Intention and Actual Turnover among Information Systems Personnel in South Africa	Smith, D. C. and Speight, H. L.
5	Globally Distributed Teams: The Effect of Diversity on Trust, Cohesion and Individual Performance	Garrison, Gary and Wakefield, Robin L. and Xu, Xiaobo and Kim, Sang Hyun
6	Stay or Quit: IT Personnel Turnover in Botswana	Uzoka, Faith-Michael E. and Mgaya, Klodwig V. and Shemi, Alice P. and Kitindi, Ernest G. and Akinnuwesi, Boluwaji A.
7	Developer Turnover in Global, Industrial Open Source Projects: Insights from Applying Survival Analysis	Lin, Bin and Robles, Gregorio and Serebrenik, Alexander
8	When and Who Leaves Matters: Emerging Results from an Empirical Study of Employee Turnover	Chatzipetrou, Panagiota and Mite, Darja and van Solingen, Rini
9	Voluntary Turnover in a Distributed Work Setting: An Examination of the Role of Spatial Proximity and Role Similarity in Project Affiliation Networks	Gopalakrishnan, Gopakumar M. and Halgin, Daniel S. and Borgatti, Stephen P.
10	Turnover in Open-Source Projects: The Case of Core Developers	Ferreira, Fabio and Silva, Luciana Lourdes and Valente, Marco Tulio
11	The Other Side of Turnover: Managing IT Personnel Strategically	Meland, Havard and Waage, Rolf Petter and Sein, Maung K.

12	Spaces of IT Intrapreneurial Freedom: A Classic Grounded Theory	Mourmant, Gaël and Niederman, Fred and Kalika, Michel
13	How Autonomy Emerges as Agile Cross-Functional Teams Mature	Lundene, Kjell and Mohagheghi, Parastoo
14	Turnover of Information Technology Professionals: The Effects of Internal Labor Market Strategies	Ang, Soon and Slaughter, Sandra
15	A Qualitative Study of the Determinants of Self-Managing Team Effectiveness in a Scrum Team	Monteiro, Cleviton V.F. and da Silva, Fabio Q.B. and dos Santos, Isabella R.M. and Farias, Felipe and Cardozo, Elisa S.F. and do A. Leitão, André R.G. and Neto, Dacio N.M. and Pernambuco Filho, Miguel J.A.
16	Who Will Leave the Company? A Large-Scale Industry Study of Developer Turnover by Mining Monthly Work Report	Bao, Lingfeng and Xing, Zhenchang and Xia, Xin and Lo, David and Li, Shanping
17	Psychological Contract in the Information Systems Profession	Moquin, René and Riemenschneider, Cindy K.
18	Satisfaction of IT Professionals with Employment Arrangements in Traditional and Virtual Contexts	Ferratt, Thomas W. and Enns, Harvey G. and Prasad, Jayesh
19	How Offshoring Affects IT Workers	Tambe, Prasanna B. and Hitt, Lorin M.
20	Exploring the Role of Mentoring in the IS Profession: A Cross-National Comparison	Adya, Monica and Cotton, John
21	How Temporal Work Styles and Product Modularity Influence Software Quality and Job Satisfaction	Foerderer, Jens and Kude, Thomas and Mithas, Sunil and Heinzl, Armin
22	Career Orientation and Organizational Commitment of IT Personnel	Sumner, Mary and Yager, Susan and Franke, Denise
23	Examining IT Professionals' Adaptation to Technological Change: The Influence of Gender and Personal Attributes	Gallivan, Michael J.
24	Achieving Equilibrium through Coworking: Work-Life Balance in	Johri, Aditya and Teo, Hon Jie

	FLOSS through Multiple Spaces and Media Use	
25	What Causes Stress in Information System Professionals?	Sethi, Vikram and King, Ruth C. and Quick, James Campbell
26	Characteristics of Collaboration in the Emerging Practice of Open Data Analysis	Choi, Joohee and Tausczik, Yla
27	How Human and Organizational Factors Influence Software Teams Productivity in COVID-19 Pandemic: A Brazilian Survey	Bezerra, Carla I. M. and de Souza Filho, Jos\{e} Cezar and Coutinho, Emanuel F. and Gama, Alice and Ferreira, Ana L\{i}via and de Andrade, Gabriel Leit\~{a}o and Feitosa, Carlos Eduardo
28	The Politics of Emotion: Exploring Emotional Labor and Political Skill across Job Types within the IT/IS Profession	Rutner, Paige S. and Irani Williams, Feruzan and Campbell, Constance and Riemenschneider, Cynthia K.
29	IT Workforce Planning: A Modular Design Science Approach	Adya, Monica and Niederman, Fred
30	Examining Career Orientations of Information Systems Personnel in an Emerging Economy Context	Mgaya, K. V. and Uzoka, Faith-Michael E. and Kitindi, E. G. and Shemi, A. P.
31	Software Development Waste	Sedano, Todd and Ralph, Paul and Praire, Cecile
32	Retention and the Career Motives of IT Professionals	Agarwal, Ritu and Ferratt, Thomas W.
33	The New Contract between IS Employees and Organizations: Workplace and Individual Factors	Burns, Mary B. and Collins, Rosann Webb
34	Single- And Double-Loop Learning: Linking Free/Libre Open Source Software (FLOSS) Developer Motivation, Contribution, and Turnover Intentions	Daniel, S. and Janansefat, S. and Dlamant, E.I. and Ren, Y.
35	The moderating roles of technological self-efficacy and time management in the technostress and employee	Yener, S. and Arslan, A. and Kilin\{S}, S.

	performance relationship through burnout	
36	When Agile Means Staying: A Moderated Mediated Model	Setor, T.K. and Joseph, D.
37	Should I stay or should I go? A study of IT professionals during a national crisis	Porto Bellini, C.G. and Palvia, P. and Moreno, V. and Jacks, T. and Graeml, A.
38	When agile means staying: The relationship between agile development usage and individual IT professional outcomes	Setor, T. and Joseph, D.
39	Relating voluntary turnover with job characteristics, satisfaction and work exhaustion-An initial study with Brazilian Developers	Massoni, T. and Ginani, N. and Silva, W. and Barros, Z. and Moura, G.
40	An empirical study on using agile methods in global software development	Vithana, V.N. and Asirvatham, D. and Johar, M.G.M.
41	Are you satisfied yet? Shared leadership, individual trust, autonomy, and satisfaction in virtual teams	Robert, L.P., Jr. and You, S.
42	Engendering cohesive software development teams: Should we focus on interdependence or autonomy?	Kakar, A.K.S.
43	How temporal work styles and product modularity influence software quality and job satisfaction	Foerderer, J. and Kude, T. and Mithas, S. and Heinzl, A.
44	IS information technology solely to blame? The influence of work-home conflict dimensions on work exhaustion	Weinert, C. and Laumer, S. and Maier, C. and Weitzel, T.
45	Control modes versus control styles: Investigating isd project control effects at the individual level	Remus, U. and Wiener, M. and Saunders, C. and Mähring, M. and Kofler, M.
46	Continuous Software Testing in a Globally Distributed Project	Moe, N.B. and Cruzes, D. and Dyba, T. and Mikkelsen, E.

47	Temporal aspects of telework and its impact on work-family conflict	Campbell, J. and Boell, S. and Keating, B. and Cecez-Kecmanovic, D.
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48	Work-life conflict and job mobility intentions	Joseph, D. and Koh, C.
49	A global perspective on information systems personnel turnover	Cha, H.S. and Quan, J.
50	IT certifications, outsourcing and information systems personnel turnover	Quan, J. and Cha, H.
51	Off-site commitment and voluntary turnover in GSD projects	Hynninen, P. and Piri, A. and Niinimäki, T.
52	Turnover intentions of Indian IS professionals	Lacity, M.C. and Iyer, V.V. and Rudramuniyaiah, P.S.
53	Information technology and the autonomy-control duality: Toward a theory	Tafti, A. and Mithas, S. and Krishnan, M.S.
54	Exploring the effects of trust, task interdependence and virtualness on knowledge sharing in teams	Staples, D. Sandy and Webster, Jane
55	Knowledge transfer in IT offshoring relationships: the roles of social capital, efficacy and outcome expectations	Zimmermann, Angelika and Ravishankar, M. N.
56	The advancement and persistence of women in the information technology profession: An extension of Ahuja's gendered theory of IT career stages	Armstrong, Deborah J. and Riemenschneider, Cynthia K. and Giddens, Laurie G.
57	From Offshore Outsourcing to Offshore Insourcing: Three Stories	Moe, Nils Brede and mite, Darja and Hanssen, Geir Kjetil
58	On the Quantification of Global Team Performance and Profitability	Zhou, Nianjun and Gifford, Wesley M. and Ratakonda, Krishna and Westerwick, Gregory H. and Engel, Carl
59	What Motivates Software Engineers Working in Global Software Development?	Beecham, Sarah and Noll, John

60	Motivating Software Engineers Working in Virtual Teams Across the Globe	Beecham, Sarah
61	A Discrepancy Model of Information System Personnel Turnover, Journal of Management Information Systems	James J. Jiang and Gary Klein
62	Exploiting Network Fusion for Organizational Turnover Prediction	Teng, Mingfei and Zhu, Hengshu and Liu, Chianren and Xiong, Hui
63	Employee Turnover Prediction: The impact of employee event features on interpretable machine learning methods	Juvitayapun, Thee
64	CoxRF: Employee Turnover Prediction based on Survival Analysis	Zhu, Quianwen and Shang, Jiaxing and Cai, Xinjun and Jiang, Linli and Feiyi, Liu and Quiang, Baohua
65	DBGE: Employee Turnover Prediction based on Dynamic Bipartite Graph Embedding	Cai, Xinjun and Shang, Jiaxing and Liu, Feiyi and Jin, Ziwei and Qiand, Baohua and Xie, Wu and Zhao, Liang
66	Who Will Leave the Company? A Large-Scale Industry Study of Developer Turnover by Mining Monthly Work Report	Bao, Lingfeng and Xing Zenchang and Xia, Xin and Lo, David and Li, Shangping
67	Predictive Modelling of Employee Turnover in Indian IT Industry Using Machine Learning Techniques	Khera, N. Shikha and Dyva

68	A Proposed Model for Predicting Employee Turnover of Information Technology Specialists Using Data Mining Techniques	Ghazi, Ahmed Hosny and Elsayed, Samir Ismail and Khedr, Elsayed Ayman
69	Employee Turnover Prediction with Machine Learning: A Reliable Approach	Zhao, Yue and Hryniewicki, Maciej and Cheng, Francesca and Fu, Boyang and Zhu, Xiaoyu
70	The Influence of Workplace Social Support on IT Professionals' Turnover Intention during the COVID-19 Crisis	Barbara Prommegger and Helmut Krcmar
71	How Human and Organizational Factors Influence Software Teams Productivity in COVID-19 Pandemic: A Brazilian Survey	Bezerra, Carla and Souza Filho, José Cezar and Coutinho, Emanuel and Ferreira, Alice Gama and Andrade, Gabriel Leão and Feitosa, Carlos
72	A Deep Dive into the Impact of COVID-19 on Software Development	Silveira Neto, Paulo Anselmo da Mota and Mannam, Umme Ayda and Almeida, Eduardo Santana de Almeida and Nagappan, Nachiappa and Lo, David, and Kochhar, Pavneet Singh, and Gao, Cuiyun and Ahmed, Iftekhar
73	Investigating the Relationship between Software Team Leadership Styles and Turnover Intention	Araújo, Narallynne and Massoni, Tiago and Sarmiento, Camila and Santos, Francielle and Oliveira, Ruan

